

The Role of Tribal Cleavage in the Breakup of Israel: A Lesson for Nigeria

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Abstract

It is not out of place to note that the Israelite community pre-monarchical period was a resemblance of the Nigerian society as we have it today due to the current experiences of the polity. There was no unified government, but a tribal system of governance just like tribalism has dominated the Nigerian political sphere. A particular judge would rise from among the tribes to lead the nation. This tribal awareness also characterised the leadership system during the monarchical period. During the reign of Saul, tribalism dominates. He appointed his tribal people to positions of honour. This tribal cleavage also rear its head during the struggle for kingship post Saul era. The tribe of Benjamin cleaved to Saul's son to rule over them while the tribe of Judah anointed David to be their ruler. The tribal cleavage continued to dominate the kingship sphere till the period of King Rehoboam, the successor of King Solomon. Unfortunately, the tribal cleavage played a prominent role in the breakup of Israel when Rehoboam made a mistake of making a wrong decision when the elders of the land visited him. They demanded that he lessen the burden laid on them by his father. This made Jeroboam announced to them that "to your tent oh! Israel." This is a great lesson for Nigeria due to the lopsided appointment of the present administration of President Muhammad Buhari. His government has been characterized by nepotism and this has deteriorated to all other vices in the country. This call for attention to prevent the nation from disintegration just like it happened in Israel then. This paper therefore employed the historical and narrative approaches in addressing this issue. The paper then concludes that the approach employed by the present administration be reversed to accommodate an inclusive form of governance that will preserve the unity and peace of the polity.

Keywords: Role, Tribal, Cleavage, Breakup and Monarchical period.

Introduction

It is not far-fetched that tribal cleavages had created enormous disunity in ancient Israel, as this is replica to the situation of the present Nigeria. This is an attempt to examine the role that tribal or established, not as a united nation, but on twelve tribe confederacy. So each tribe was existing on its own. It became pronounced during the time of Solomon. Solomon exempted his own tribe from forced labour. One of the core challenges confronting Nigeria system of governance now is the perpetual occurrence of tribal cleavage that has led to laments from the people. Apparently, the high rate of uncooperativeness elucidates that, the country's unity is not thriving. Consequently, the streets and roads are crowded with both juveniles and adults struggling to earn a living. The quest to become the president of the nation is on the high gear with the rate of campaign that has intensified. Governance unproductiveness seems to have a direct link with the corrupt practices of Nigerian political leaders, and its aftermath is the sufferings of the citizenry who bears the brunt.

The Influence of Monarchical Government on the Nation of Israel

Saul was Israel's first king. His kingship was of a primitive kind in which the king functioned as a military leader rather than as a King. Saul's reign was followed by that of David and Solomon. They were the only Israelite kings who ruled over both the northern and southern kingdoms in a personal union commonly called the monarchy. David reigned for 33 years over all twelve tribes (2 Samuel 5:5). He was succeeded by Solomon, who reigned for 40 years after being crowned as king when the aged David was still alive (1 Kings 1:32-48). The monarchy lasted for about 70 years and came to a sudden end after Solomon's death. Even though the kingdom was divided at that time, the roots

of this division may be traced far back into the history of Israel. In part, the division resulted from David and Solomon's tailor-made monarchy as well as the developments that took place after the death of Solomon. In this article, there are underlying factors that influenced the division of Israel's monarchy. Each of these underlying factors has impacted upon the history of Israel with various degrees of intensity. At times, they were initiated for the sake of the nation, whilst at other times they were driven by egoistic motives. Be that as it may, the result was a national disaster that was never overcome in Israel's history. Nevertheless, the hope of a re-united monarchy remained alive for the envisioned glorious, eschatological future (Ezekiel 37:15-28). It was a messianic symbolic act that Jesus called twelve disciples, signifying his claim for the twelve tribes of Israel, because the reestablishment of the twelve tribes of Israel was seen as God's saving act at the beginning of the messianic age.¹

The Pre-monarchical Confederacy in the Land of Israel

The First Book of Samuel marks the transition of Israel from a fractious coalition of tribes to a monarchy with a central government in Jerusalem. The story begins with the birth and calling of the prophet Samuel and continues with the call to kingship and the reigns of Saul and David. This is the story of state formation, the centralization of power and of worship, and the establishment of a new political, military, and social order.² From the closing words of the book of Judges and the opening chapters of 1 Samuel we know that the Israelites are both leaderless and disconnected from God. The closest thing they have to a national leader is the priest Eli, who with his sons runs the shrine at Shiloh. The Israelites' political, military, and economic prosperity depends on their faithfulness to God. So the people bring their offerings and sacrifices to God at the shrine, but the priests make a mockery of interaction with God. "Now the sons of Eli were scoundrels...for they treated the offerings of the Lord with contempt"(1 Sam. 2: 12 – 17). They are untrustworthy as human leaders, and they do not honor God in their hearts. Worshipers find that those who should direct them toward an experience of worship are instead stealing from them.³

Somewhat ominously for a nation about to become a monarchy, the first thing we observe is that inherited authority is inherently dangerous for two reasons. The first is that there is no guarantee that descendants of even the greatest leader will be competent and faithful. The second is that being born to power is often a corrupting influence itself, resulting all too often either in complaisance or—as the case of Eli's sons—entitlement. Eli performs his work as a sacred charge from God (1 Sam. 2:25), but his sons see it as a personal possession (1 Sam. 2:14). Growing up in an atmosphere somewhat analogous to a family business, they expect from a young age to inherit their father's privileges. Because this "family business" is God's own shrine—giving the family a claim to divine authority over the populace—his sons' malfeasance is all the more injurious.⁴

If not his scoundrel sons, who would succeed Eli as priest? 1 Samuel 3:1-4:1 and 1 Samuel 7:3-17 reveal God's plan to raise up young Samuel to succeed Eli. Samuel receives one of the few audible calls from God recorded in the Bible, but notice that this is *not* a call to a type of work or ministry. (Samuel had been serving in the house of the Lord since he was two or three years old, and the choice of occupation had been made by his mother. See 1 Samuel 1:20-28 and 2:18-21.) Nonetheless it is a call to a task, namely to tell Eli that God has decided to punish him and his sons, who are soon to be removed as God's priests. After fulfilling this calling, Samuel continues to serve under Eli until he is recognized as a prophet in his own right (1 Sam. 4:1) and succeeds Eli after Eli's death (1 Sam. 4:18). Samuel becomes the leader of God's people, not because of self-serving ambition or a sense of entitlement, but because God had given him a vision (1 Sam. 3:10-14) and the gifts and skills to lead people to carry out that vision (1 Sam. 3:19-4:1).⁵

It is not clear whether the corruption of the leader, Eli, causes the corruption of the people or vice versa, but chapters 4-6 depict the disaster that befalls those who are poorly governed. Israel has been engaged in a centuries-long struggle against the neighboring country of the Philistines. A new attack is made by the Philistines, which routs the Israelites, resulting in 4,000 casualties (1 Sam. 4:1-3). The Israelites recognize the defeat as a sign of God's disfavor. But instead of examining their fault, repenting, and coming to the Lord for guidance, they try to manipulate God into serving their purposes. They fetch the ark of the covenant of God and charge into battle

against the Philistines, assuming that the ark will make them invincible. Eli's sons lend an aura of authority to the plan. But the Philistines slaughter Israel in the battle, killing 30,000 Israelite soldiers, capturing the ark, slaying Eli's sons and causing Eli's own death (1 Sam. 4:4-19).⁶

Eli's sons, alongside the leaders of the army, made the mistake of thinking that because they bore the name of God's people and possessed the symbols of God's presence, they were in command of God's power. Perhaps those in charge believed they could actually control God's power by carrying around the ark. Or maybe they had deceived themselves into thinking that because they were God's people, whatever they wanted for themselves would be what God wanted for them. In any case, they discovered that God's presence is not a warrant to project God's power, but an invitation to receive God's guidance. Ironically, the ark contained the greatest means of God's guidance—the Ten Commandments (Deut. 10:5)—but Eli's sons did not bother to seek any kind of guidance from God before attacking the Philistines.⁷ The Philistines fare no better with the ark than the Israelites did, and it becomes a dangerous property for both sides until it is retired from military use and Samuel calls Israel to recommit themselves to the Lord himself (1 Sam. 5:1-7:3). The people heed his call and turn back to worshipping the Lord, and Samuel's career expands rapidly. His role as priest soon grows to "judge" (meaning a military governor) and he leads the successful defense against the Philistines (1 Sam. 7:4-13). His roll soon encompasses holding court for legal matters (1 Sam. 10:16). Behind all his tasks lies his calling to be "a trustworthy prophet of the Lord" (1 Sam. 3:20).⁸

As Samuel ages, he repeats Eli's error and appoints his own sons to succeed him. Like Eli's sons, they turn out to be greedy and corrupt (1 Sam. 8:1-3). Disappointing sons of great leaders is a recurrent theme in Samuel and Kings. (The tragedy of David's son Absalom occupies the bulk of 2 Samuel chapters 13-19, to which we will return. It reminds us that the work of parenting is as challenging as every other occupation but far more emotionally intense. No solution is given in the text, but we can observe that Eli, Samuel, and David seem to have given their troubled children many privileges but little paternal involvement. Yet we also know that even the most dedicated parents may face the heartbreak of wayward children. Rather than laying blame or stereotyping causes, let us simply note that parenting children is an occupation requiring as much prayer, skill, community support, good fortune, and love as any other, if not more. Ultimately to be a parent—whether our children bring delight, disappointment, or some of both—is to depend on God's grace and mercy and to hope for a redemption beyond what we see during our lifetimes. Perhaps our deepest comfort is to remember that God also experienced a parent's heartbreak for his condemned Son, yet overcame all through the power of love.⁹

Seeing the unsuitability of Samuel's sons, the Israelites ask him to "appoint for us, then, a king to govern us, like other nations." This request displeases Samuel (1 Sam. 8:4-6). Samuel warns the people that kings lay heavy burdens on a nation. It was stated:

These will be the ways of the king who will reign over you: he will take your sons and appoint them to his chariots and to be his horsemen to run before his chariots; and he will appoint for himself commanders of thousands and commanders of fifties, and some to plow his ground and to reap his harvest, and make his implements of war and the equipment of his chariots. He will take your daughters to be perfumers and cooks and bakers. He will take the best of your fields and vineyards and olive orchards and give them to his courtiers. (1 Sam. 8:10-17).¹⁰

In fact, the kings would be so rapacious that eventually the people would cry out to God to save them from the kings (1 Sam. 8:18). God agrees that asking for a king is a bad idea because it amounts to a rejection of God himself, as king. Nonetheless, the Lord decides to allow the people to choose their form of government, and he tells Samuel, "Listen to the voice of the people in all that they say to you; for they have not rejected you, but they have rejected me from being king over them" (1 Sam. 8:7). Sometimes God permits institutions that are not part of his eternal purpose, and the monarch of Israel is one of the most glaring examples.¹¹

Both God and Samuel showed great humility, resilience, and grace in allowing Israel to make choices and mistakes, learning from the consequences. There are many institutional and workplace situations where leadership must adjust to people's poor choices, yet at the same time try to provide opportunities for growth and grace.

Samuel's warning to Israel could easily serve as a warning to nations, businesses, churches, schools, and other organizations of today's world. In our fallen world, people abuse power, and we have to adjust while at the same time doing what we can to change things. Our aspiration is to love God and treat other people as God commands in the law given to Moses, which God's people have had an extremely hard time doing in every age.¹² The final account of Samuel's governance (1 Sam. 7:15-17) says that he went on a circuit of the cities of Israel year by year to the cities of Israel, governing and administering justice. The chapter closes with, "And he built there an altar to the Lord." His civic and military services to Israel were founded on his life-long faithfulness and worship of the Lord.

Tribal Cleavages: A Reflection on the Reign of Saul to Solomon

Continuous antagonism and power struggle between various tribes. Pre-monarchic Israel did not begin as a homogeneous nation. It became a nation over a long period of time. The Biblical narratives recall how the nation evolved through the joining of diverse groups of people (Exo. 12:38; Judg. 1:16). They were a "mixed group, by no means all descendants of Jacob". They did not gather around one sacred (sacred) place as a twelve-tribe amphictyony. Modern scholarship favours different models for Israel's early history but agrees that diverse groups formed the later nation. The rivalry between the tribes and their different history in pre-monarchic times may reflect an ethnic and political division that was probably supported by religious diversity. Sporadically calls for a monarchy were generally rejected. They were either abandoned immediately (Judges 8:22-23), or rejected after a short period of time (cf. Judg. 9:22-23ff).¹³

According to the Book of Judges, whilst some tribes formed coalitions, they also turned against each other at various times (cf. e. g. Judges 20). Furthermore, not all tribes were held in the same esteem. For example, antagonism seems to have been directed against the Ephraimites in particular, as Judges records two occasions where they complained that they had not been asked to join a battle (Judges 8:1-3; 12:1-6). When Saul was made king, he took up the charismatic role of the judges. His kingship did not constitute a centralised monarchy with the hegemony of one tribe. Rather, Saul had been chosen as king to act as an elected military leader on a permanent basis. This was done because of the constant threat posed by the Philistines, the nomads of the desert, and the Canaanites. He struggled throughout his reign to stabilise Israel but failed. At the time of his death, he left behind a country in crisis. When David became king, the kingship was transferred from the tribe of Benjamin to that of Judah. The tribe of Ephraim had never been well-accepted, but demanded a superior position. Later, in the Northern Kingdom, Ephraim's superior position is still evident. Ephraim is even used synonymously for Israel (2 Chron. 25:7; Isa. 7:2).¹⁴

There was no reason for all the tribes to accept David as king immediately, as kingship was still foreign to Israel, and its implications still undefined. David faced opposition from the leader of Saul's army, Abner, who was related to the king's house (1 Sam. 17:20). He supported Ishbaal, the son of Saul, and made him king. Ishbaal lacked the people's support because he did not fulfil the original expectation of a king that is being a successful military leader. As a result of Philistine dominion, David initially ruled over a very limited kingdom, viz. the Transjordanian territory. The tribes of Gilead, Ephraim, and Benjamin as well as the people of Jezreel, a city in Issachar and the Ashurites in the main supported Ishbaal (2 Sam. 2:8-10). It was only after Ishbaal's assassination (2 Sam. 4:7) that David gained control over all Israel (2 Sam. 5:1-3), uniting the royal office of two kingdom, namely Israel and Judah (2 Samuel 5:5; 11:11), in a personal union.¹⁵

Sheba's revolt took place during David's reign. Sheba was a member of Saul's tribe and had been living in Ephraim (2 Samuel 20:21). He might have hoped to get tribal support from the Northern tribes, who were negative towards David's monarchy. Sheba's war-cry (2 Samuel 20:1) is almost identical with the one of the secessionists under Rehoboam (1 Kgs. 12:16). The narrator clearly prepares his case that the disunity and constant animosity of the Northern tribes was a major factor of the schism. Abner had been the commander-in-chief of the army under the reigns of Saul (1 Samuel 14:50; 17:55) and Ishbaal (2 Samuel 2:8). During Ishbaal's reign, David had already formed a new army whose members came from Judah. There were two chief commanders in the army, one for Judah and one for Israel. "Abner son of Ner, was commander of the army of Israel, and Amasa son of Jether,

was commander of the army of Judah” (1 Kings 2:32). After David had established the monarchy, he took the co-ordination of these two armies under his control. He created a new office and put Joab, his faithful friend, in control of the army (2 Samuel 8:16). The extended influence of the royal family weakened the distribution of power. The power of the kingdom was maintained through the extended influence of the royal family. The latter occupied the important positions in the government and elsewhere. For example, David made his nephews (1 Chronicles 2:16.17) commanders of the army. First Joab and later Amasa.¹⁶

The Impact of Tribal Cleavages on Nigeria Political System and National Development

Tribalism is coined from ‘tribes’, an alternative word for ethnic or linguistic groups or in some countries ‘nation’ or ‘nationality’. Tribes supply a lot of Nigeria’s diversity providing traditional costumes, dress, music, dancing, indigenous language, arts, folklore, religion, all of which can constitute an asset to a people. It is naturally regarded as a small group, a human social organization defined by ‘traditions of common descent’ having temporary or permanent political integration above the family level with a shared language, culture or ideology. *Encyclopaedia Britannica* asserts that tribe members ‘share a tribe name in a contiguous territory, and engage in joint endeavours such as trade, agriculture, house construction, warfare, economic and business activities and warfare. They often stay in small cluster-communities which can grow into large communities and even a nation. This paper attempts to critically examine the multiple play-outs of Nigeria’s many tribes and nationalities during and after colonialism, the intricate connection between tribalism and politics, leadership and the evolution of the Nigerian polity, the grievous harm as well as advantages of tribalism to Nigeria’s evolution. The tribe is always a major factor in the country and in its people. It ends with specific prognosis and a few recommendations.¹⁷

Mainstream literature on social cleavages reflects the existence of competing definitions of the concept embedded in contrasting approaches to analysis. It also suggests substantial intersections in research interest. The most frequently addressed issue arguably remains attempts at establishing a correlation between social cleavages and the characteristics of political conflict or contestation. Principal amongst such studies is that of, Lipset, which use the term ‘cleavage’ to refer to conflict groups based on perceptions of association in Ethnic Identity as a Social Cleavage in Nigeria. Cleavages ‘originate’ in the social realm. They are politicized, however, as they become issues of large-scale conflict and become tied to political parties. Implicit here is the conceptualization of social cleavage as a type of political division based on major social division. The central assumption of all such analyses is that the particular manner in which members of a society differ from and socialize with one another in regard to political issues has major, direct and specifiable concerns for political contests. Different patterns of social divisions with different underlying notions will have diverse political repercussions both at domestic and regional levels. Inclusionary notions and policies are likely to foster peaceful coexistence in both the country and the region.

Heterogeneous or homogenous all societies are split along one or more social distinctions, or cleavages. The study suggests, often than not, these cleavages transform into fault lines or mediums along which political attitudes form and podiums for political competitions or conflicts as the case may be. Various schools of thoughts have proffered varying theoretical and empirical interpretations and clarifications, which seek to in amongst others rationalize the existence and influence of social cleavages. For instance, Karl Marx contends social class determines everything, that it was the only important social cleavage. In this line of thought, the argument is based on claims that the social class one belongs to determine their political attitude. Put differently, whether one was bourgeois or proletarian determined most political orientations. Class cleavages, demonstrably obvious because of industrialization, did not become politicized until socialist parties explicitly articulated the interest of the working class. While class matters significantly, evidence abounds to suggests, class and political orientations are not necessarily exclusive, and that other factors such as race, geography, education, economy, ethnicity and others could also inform one’s political orientation.

The question in the context does not challenge the significance of class; rather it argues that class and other factors affect political orientation. Hence class might be a sufficient condition for forming cleavages, but

are not necessary conditions. Even in the advanced west, class as social cleavage has overtime fallen short of accounting for group political orientation, in the wake of nationalist agenda as witnessed in the Brexit saga and European integration. The situation is however more pronounced in developing countries like Nigeria, where class rarely serve as a basis for formation of social cleavages, given the near absence of formidable class structures in such societies. Against this backdrop, beyond the social stratifications or division, this research emphasizes the role of actors in streamlining such political conflicts, which includes but not necessarily limited to, competition for resources and political power along social distinctions such as ethnicity, culture and religion.¹⁸

This line of thought derives predominantly from a logic which suggests social groups like ethnicity in their latent or symbolic form may serve as basis for social classification, without the instrumentality of key actors however, they fall in driving political conflicts or otherwise. Arguably, in the absence of formidable class structures as emphasized above, ethnicity which intersects like religion and culture in Nigeria, remains an enduring feature of social distinction in pre-colonial and contemporary Nigeria. In lieu, it is the opinion of the research that, class cleavage barely holds water and remains dismal in accounting for social norms and conformity in Nigeria, rather ethnicity which cuts across class seems a more viable political currency.¹⁹

The second, urban-rural cleavage which again accompanies industrialization has little relevance in Africa in the way we know it from Western Europe. It describes the conflict of interest between the mercantile and industrial bourgeoisie on the one hand, and of the feudal landowners on the other hand. Increasing urbanization in Africa might provide the potential for a conflict between the urban and rural population (e.g. about the pricing of basic foodstuffs). Up till now, this has not been developed into a clear cut line of cleavage and, more importantly, into specific political party formations or orientations. One reason might be that urbanization, which is not linked to industrialization in Africa, is, sociologically, to some degree only an extension of the village into the (shanty) town, and the urban and rural population maintains close personal links as well as their ethnic identity.²⁰

Recommendations

When trying to offer practical solutions for the resolution and/or management of ethnic conflict, it has to be borne in mind that one is almost always faced with a multi-faceted issue containing numerous complexities the case of Nigeria being no exception. Not being intimately familiar with all these intricacies certainly detracts from any suggestions offered, but every attempt is a step closer to realising the ultimate goal, just as every drop fills the bucket. Firstly, let us have a look at the challenges facing Nigeria under Buhari challenges that ethnic conflict management will obviously have to take into account. According to Solomon, these challenges include the following: To forge a united Nigeria out of 250 fractious ethnic groups; to limit the power of the military, while ensuring its maintenance as a source of stability in West Africa; to inculcate a culture respectful of human rights and the rule of law; to increase economic performance while simultaneously developing an understanding of the need for a more equitable distribution of the country's wealth; and to put an end to spiraling levels of crime and corruption through effective, good governance.

In Nigeria, there are three main levels of leadership that can potentially participate in the negotiations process, namely the federal government under Obasanjo, the state governments and the leaders of the various ethnic groups outside of these structures. Under the initiative of the federal government, determining the various leaderships to participate in the negotiations process can take place both horizontally (e. g. Obasanjo and his cabinet with National Assembly or between groups on grassroots level etc.) and vertically (e. g. federal government with state governments). During these preliminary talks (as well as later on) issues such as ideology and religion should be downplayed to a minimum, as only a basis for future talks and negotiations are being formed. These talks can then be gradually intensified and broadened to encompass other issues as well. It should be stressed that this process must be as inclusive and representative as possible. Clearly a higher degree of government centralization should be introduced in order to circumvent many problems of the past. As an example, the number of states should be kept to a minimum, as their proliferation intensified competition for federal resources in the past, and so contributed to ethnic conflict and fragmentation.

A higher degree of state centralization will obviously be conducive to uniting Nigeria, but will not succeed in bringing this about on its own. It should be accompanied by nation-building and the forging of a common Nigerian identity based on symbolism and the spirit of ubuntu. These symbols should incorporate as many of the symbols cherished by the various population groups as possible, while combined with totally new ones. The alternative is that an entirely new set of symbols be introduced. In the negotiation process, the details of these and other important issues such as the division of power can be worked out, but we do think that a limited party system, similar to the two party system under Babangida, will be more effective than a multi-party system, as it will force political parties to gain support nationally instead of relying on traditional bases of support, and contribute to a unified nationhood in which each person will see him/herself as a Nigerian first of all. Indeed, the powerful effects of a national pride should not be underrated.

In addition, the results of the negotiations should be contained in a constitution that clearly specifies all aspects of the political and other systems as agreed between the negotiating parties. A charter of human rights should form a main part of this document, while the constitution should clearly make provisions for establishing the rule of law principle. It is further important that the provisions of the constitution remain rooted in reality, while the judiciary should be sufficiently strengthened to uphold it. In our estimation, the economic factors should be viewed as the key to the effective management of ethnic conflict in Nigeria. Revenues from oil especially, should be managed in such a way, that each community sees substantial benefits emanating from their peaceful participation in both the political and economic processes, instead of competing with one another for federal resources. The federal government should still be the primary administrator of these revenues, and allocate at least 30% of the revenues, whether from oil or other economic activities, to the area in which it is generated. Conversely, communities can be provided with different benefits, for instance in the form of housing or infrastructure. Instead of antagonizing local leaders, or the communities themselves, the federal government should involve them as much as possible in the decision-making process of how resources should be allocated. In this process, both the positions of the federal government and these leaders can be strengthened based on the principle of interdependence.

Special attention should be paid to the economic situation in poorer northern Nigeria, especially by focusing on issues such as illiteracy, development of trade and industry, better agricultural methods and the development of infrastructure. Perhaps this can be done in forging partnership programs between the north and the south. As the north presently fears the better-educated south, southerners might even be encouraged to participate in federally and privately funded education programs in the north, for example. One of the most important things to bear in mind, though, is that it is absolutely crucial to bring about positive changes and improvements in the living standards of the population and to eradicate inequality among them in other words, just like with every issue tackled in managing ethnic conflict in Nigeria, there should be tangible benefits to persuade the people to actively participate in the process, including concrete signs that the government is doing its best to root out corruption and to deliver maximum benefits to its citizens. Regarding religious issues, it is more difficult to suggest any solutions. Solutions may be forthcoming from the negotiating process, but to our mind, these negotiations should take part between the religious groups themselves, rather than as part of the formal negotiations. As religious matters are highly contentious in the Nigerian society, we think that there should be a total division between the secular state and the religious institutions. In other words, the state should not involve itself in purely religious affairs and vice versa. The military should also be restructured to reflect the values of a transforming Nigeria. Changes in leadership of the armed forces will already be a positive step forward (as Obasanjo has already done), but a sufficient system of checks and balances should be implemented in order to ensure that the Nigerian executive maintains control over them. It might also be a good idea to include members of the armed forces in the negotiation process, and afterwards to persuade them that, by serving the interests of the democracy, they are serving the interests of Nigeria and its people.

Conclusion

Abstract

Tribalism is coined from 'tribes', an alternative word for ethnic or linguistic groups or in some countries 'nation' or 'nationality'. Tribes supply a lot of Nigeria's diversity providing traditional costumes, dress, music, dancing, indigenous language, arts, folklore, religion, all of which can constitute an asset to a people. It is naturally regarded as a small group, a human social organization defined by 'traditions of common descent' having temporary or permanent political integration above the family level with a shared language, culture or ideology.

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Keywords: tribalism, ethnicity, federalism, constitution, natio

Ethnic conflicts are some of the major challenges facing the world, and Nigeria in particular, today. These conflicts also have a compounding influence on other issues such as political, economic and social stability. The case of ethnic conflict in Nigeria is illustrative of this point, and indeed multi-faceted and extremely complex. Although many positive steps have already been taken by the present democratic government of Obasanjo in the direction of addressing this conflict and other problems facing Nigeria, it is clear that much more still has to be done especially in the light of the recent heightening of ethnic tensions. In this context, it is hoped that the modest practical suggestions made above may contribute to the process of finding a solution to this pressing problem.

Endnotes

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